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LEGACY OF EMPIRE**

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ZIONISTIC SETTLER COLONIALISM: THE LEGACY OF EMPIRE

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ABSTRACT

The Palestine issue involves historical, political, territorial and religious dispute between Israel and Palestinians. Two key factors or reasons, Zionism and Imperialism, are responsible for the birth of this conflict. Since its birth this issue holds a significant place in international community. United States has been a key ally and supported Israel every time since its birth in 1948. This alliance is based on shared strategic interests and historical connections. Washington has its own reasons for the involvement in Middle East such as oil reservoirs, economic interests and strategic interests. The formation of Israel is a complex historical process shaped by a convergence of factors including the Zionist movement, geopolitical considerations, Imperial interests and the aftermath of World War II. The ongoing challenges in the region underscore the need for continued efforts to address the deep-rooted issues and work toward a comprehensive and sustainable resolution.

Keywords: Zionism, Diaspora, Settler Colonialism, European Imperialism, Jews claim Nakba.

Introduction:

Hazrat Noah had three sons: Ham, Shem and Japheth. Generations of these three sons settled all around the world. The descendants of Canaan, a son of Shem, settled in the region of Palestine. In the early periods, the name of the Palestine was Canaan and the people who lived there are called Canaanites.¹ It was a land of Prophets and Almighty Allah send so many prophets here to establish peace, justice and spiritual harmony among human civilizations. This land has its own importance in human civilizations due to its political, social and religious significance. It is located at the crossroad of the three continents and the followers of three major religions of the word have religious sentiments attached with this region. These religions are Islam, Christianity and Judaism. But unfortunately, followers of all these religions often fought each other due to some reasons or others. Among all these reasons, political reason is the most important. Palestine has a long history of invasion and tyranny. Tribes of Jews invaded the land of Canaan in twelfth century BC. At that time Canaan was not a land without population. They build a strong kingdom under the rule of Hazrat Solomon but collapsed after some centuries. Romans conquered the land from Jews but after some time they accepted Christianity as a religion. So, this land came under the rule of followers of Christianity. After the 7th century, Muslims took control of this land from the Christians. After that history witnessed the cruel and shameful history of Western Colonialism. Jews were scattered all over the world after their Diaspora which started two thousands years ago. They lived under both the Christian and Muslim rule but the condition of their living under

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the Christian rule was totally different from the condition under Muslim rule. In European countries persecutions, killings and burnings of Jews were common and they were compelled to stay in closed ghettos.²

Last two centuries proved to be political tumultuous and lots of changes happened in geographical conditions of the world. New modern states were emerged on the map of the globe with the right of self-determination. Due to the movement of these nation states and the concept of nationalism made Jews realize to have their own nation state. They politically united under a movement called Zionism. It was a movement with colonial ambitions that envaded the Palestine to colonize the land by penetrating into the heart of the Arab world. After the birth of Zionism, the history revolves over the series of incidents among Britain, French, American and the people of Zionist ideology. The founders of the Zionism were well aware that they couldn't able to achieve their goal of separate national state without the help of imperial powers. They ensured a necessary position, by aligning with British and Americans later on, to fulfill their nefarious motives. Starting in the 1880s, the Zionist movement supported migration of Jews and set up colonies in Palestine. They spread a false and racist idea that Palestine was a promised land for the Jews as it was a land without people and as if history stood still for two thousands year. Under British mandate period, Jews enjoyed the full support of Britain to carry out the ethnic cleansing of the indigenous population and paved a way for the creation of the state of Israel. After 2nd World War, they changed their imperial ally, Americans instead of Britain, to fulfill their nefarious interests of colonizing the Palestine. League of Nations and UN were used as tools by all the colonial powers to procure their interests. David Ben-Gurion announced the birth of the Israel in 1948 and after 10 minutes President Harry Truman granted American recognition of the new state that was established by displacement of native population.³ Due to the formation of settlements on the land of Palestine and simultaneously removing the natives, Israel has been treated as an example of the settler state throughout this paper. The formation of Israel had profound implications not only for the immediate region but also for global politics. It is the hot burning issue of the modern day time and need to be resolved; otherwise, the consequences can be dire.

Purpose of the study:

The aim and objectives of the study is to:

- Know the nature, meaning and history of Settler Colonialism.
- Get acquaintance with the origin, history and ideology of Zionism.
- Analyze the relationship of Zionism and Imperialism in colonial framework.
- Prove that Zionism was a colonial ideology to form Jewish National State.
- Analyze the claim of "The Promised Land" by Jews in Biblical Studies.

Methodology:

Based on the qualitative research, after thoroughly examined the data, the methodology employed in the study is historical as well descriptive and analytical. The relevant date which is collected includes books, research papers published in reputed journals, newspapers like New York Times and Washington Post, magazines published in the different countries of the world particularly The Journal of Arab Studies Quarterly, Palestine Studies, and Middle East Journal, etc.

Settler Colonialism:

Settlement has always been among the basic needs of human being. He continues to migrate from one place to other because of his safe and better future. It is a natural phenomenon that historically continues. If it includes tyranny, oppression and exploitation, it is called colonialism. According to the Dictionary of Politics:

“Colonialism: Strictly referred to the policies and methods by which an imperial power-maintained and extended its control over other territories or people; now more frequently used in a pejorative sense.”⁴

Colonialism refers to a system that allows powerful state or society to establish control beyond its geographic borders for its economic benefits. It is such a political, social and cultural system in which a powerful state dominates the weaker one through technology and military might. It enforces its culture, traditions, ideologies and laws by force and oppression. It refers to the invasion and control of other people’s land and resources.⁵ Imperialism and colonialism are often use interchangeably. Imperialism is a policy or practice of extending power and dominion by gaining political and military control. It means the practice, the theory and the attitude of domination while colonialism is a consequence of this theory.⁶ It is a coercive system for controlling the distant lands to promotes the political and economic interests of the empire. The ideology that is common in both of them is; exploitation, oppression and tyranny. As colonialism is a phenomenon that has shaped human settlement all over the world, it continues to wear different masks according to the ground realities. One of the worst mask or stage is “Settler Colonialism”. According Oxford dictionary, a person who goes to live a new country or region is called a “settler”.⁷ When this phenomenon is done on a large scale and it includes genocide, oppression, exploitation and colonial ideology, it is called settler colonialism.

“Settler colonialism is a specific mode of domination where a community of exogenous settlers permanently displaces to a new locale, eliminates or displaces indigenous populations and sovereignties, and constitutes an autonomous political body.”⁸

It is a system of oppression that aims to displace indigenous people and replace them with new settlers. It is based on genocide by which colonizer invade and occupy the land permanently. It can be distinguished from other form of colonialism in many ways but two key features are most important. First, settlers come to stay and occupy the land permanently. They assert sovereignty over indigenous people. Second, settler colonialism is an ongoing process which eliminates the indigenous population by genocide, force and exploitation of their resources.

History witnessed the settler colonialism in America, Australia, New Zealand and Africa but the worst form of settler colonialism is the state of Israel. It colonized the Palestine land and population with the help of European imperial powers. European imperialism colonized more than half of the world for five centuries. In last century the shameful and cruel history of European imperialism ended. Modern nation states emerged on the globe with the right of self determination. In Middle East, the imperial powers joined hands together with the Zionistic movement to serve their interests in the territory. During the last phase of an Ottoman Empire, the Zionist colonization started and flourished under the umbrella of British Imperialism. Due to Zionist-Imperialist alliance people of Palestine find themselves in the paws of imperial powers and Zionists. They lost the political and physical control over their own land. The tragedy faced by the Palestinians in the mid of

20th century, symbolizes the nature of the Zionist movement which unfolded itself in the late nineteenth century.⁹ Most of us are aware that Zionist Israel was founded on the basis of historical promises made by imperial powers but Jews claim that it was based on theological promises. Palestine-Israel conflict has become the most significant issue of the modern age. Due to this conflict the global peace is at stake and the clouds of third world war are hovering.

Jews claim on “The Promised Land”:

Jews claim that Israel came into being as a result of a promise made by God. It was established due to certain biblical prophecies and religious claims. God promised Hazrat Abraham that He would give the land to his descendants.¹⁰ The land (from Egypt to the Euphrates River) was described as flowing with milk and honey. God also said that the land was the homeland of the various tribes.¹¹ Because of this promise Jews believe that much of the Middle East belongs to them today.

1- Promise with Conditions: They interpret the verses of promise in such a way that, the promise seems unconditional and forever. But the detailed and through Biblical study reveals that this promise was not unconditional and to gain the land they had to fulfill their promise too. Foremost promise was to believe in Oneness of God and follow the righteous path. If the people of Israel do not fulfill the terms of the covenants it would be broken and they will lose the inheritance of the promised-land.¹² But history shows us that they rebelled against god and worshiped or served the other idols. They killed the messengers of Him and indulged in shameful blasphemies. They openly turned down the commandments and strayed from the righteous path. Because of their disobedience, God warned them with death, hunger, destruction and fear.¹³ He also said that if they do not change their attitude of disobedience they will be forbidden entering to the land of Israel.¹⁴ Because of their attitude and disobedience, Allah, the Almighty, cursed and scattered them. They were also deprived of their promised land.

2- Promise fulfilled: According to the Jews, they never possessed the entire Promised Land, so the promises have not yet been fulfilled. But many verses of Bible show that the entire land was given to the Jews under the leadership of Joshua and they were twice exiled from the land because of their disobedience and heinous crimes.

“The Jews did return to Judea, they did rebuild the walls of Jerusalem and they did rebuild the temple; and after fluctuating fortunes, they did secure a brief period of political independence and expansion under the Maccabees.”¹⁵

Now, it is clear that the prophecies have been filled, thus can never be fulfilled again.

3- Covenant and the prophet Ismael: Old Testament said that God made promise with Abraham and his descendants after him. As Hazrat Ismael was also a seed of Abraham but Jews claim that this covenant was established with Hazrat Ishaq only. According to Jews he was the child of Abraham’s concubine that is why covenant was not established for Hazrat Ismael. The argument of Jews couldn’t be accepted according to historical determination. First, Hazrat Ismael was not a son of concubine. Second, when Hazrat Abraham made a covenant with God he had only one son, Hazrat Ismael. Hazrat Ishaq was not born at that time. Apart from this Hazrat Abraham had six son too from his third wife.¹⁶ Covenant was made to the seeds of Hazrat Abraham and Hazrat Ismael also belongs to seed of Hazrat Abraham, so in real sense the descendants of Hazrat Ismael are too are the legitimate heir of Hazrat Abraham.¹⁷

Zionism: History and Ideologies

“Chosen people of God” were thrown out and expelled by the Romans in 70 C.E from Jerusalem. Jewish State was destroyed, Mount Temple was demolished and the Jews were scattered throughout the world. Their Diaspora continued till the 20th century. They could never mix with the local population due to religious bias and conspirational character. They have always been hostile to every society because they rebelled against the Church, exploited trade and economy, interfered in political affairs and remained isolated from the common population. They were never accepted by any society rather in Muslim Spain where they found peace and prosperity. Most of the Jews called it the golden period of their Diaspora. Europeans never tolerated the Jews, who were alienated by their apartness and non-conformism. During this Diaspora, the ideology of “Chosen people of God” and “The Promised Land” became the integral part of their national consciousness. However, Jews and history both entered the nineteenth century. Socio-Political circumstances or challenges facing Europe in nineteenth century caused birth of a movement called “Zionism”. This term was first coined by Nathan in 1890. It is considered the Jewish national movement seeking return of the Jews to their promised land, Palestine. This movement emerged in the half of the nineteenth century. To find out the roots, nature and dynamics of this movement, one must look into the triple dynamics that shaped the essence of nineteenth century Europe: Anti-Semitism, Nationalism and Colonialism.¹⁸

Anti-Semitism: it is evident that socially, economically and politically, the nineteenth century was the most revolutionary era of the Jews history. As it is narrated above, due to their prejudice character and religious ideas they were not generally accepted by the European societies. They were facing political, economic and social discrimination and were struggling for their civic and legal rights. At that time there was a common saying “Jews are the cause of each trouble” echoed the whole Europe.¹⁹ This Western attitude set the stage for this movement called Anti-Semitism. Wilhelm Marr, a German Thinker, presented this term in 1873 in his work, *The Victory of Judaism over Germandom*.²⁰ He proposed the idea that Jews were conspiring and trying to interfere in the state affairs so they should be excluded from citizenship. Under the influence of this movement, there started pogroms, persecution and tyranny against Jews in Russia, Romania and Poland. This movement made lives of Jews miserable all over the Europe. This was the time when Jews thinkers and philosophers started to think about separate homeland. They came to the conclusion that without their separate homeland they would never be come out of this miserable plight.

Nationalism: The growth and expansion of European imperialism reawakened the idea in the hearts of the Jews that they too should have separate territory as a nation. If European nations had expended themselves into the other continents, why not Jewish state, they argued. For Zionism then, “colonization would be the instrument of nation building not the by product of an already fulfilled nationalism”.²¹ The European nationalism was based on racism, exploitation and superiority and Zionism also claimed the racial unity of Jews and religious nation state. European nations had a civilizing mission of “White man’s burden” by Kipling as the driving force for their cruel and shameful act of colonizing. Such notions and ideas played a key role in the emergence of Zionism.

Colonization: Due to expansion in colonialism, the need to secure the trade and military route was foremost important. The geographical position of the Middle East as the gateway to Africa and the bridge to Asia made it more valuable in the eyes of the imperial powers. The importance of the Arab land intensified as the “Sick man of Europe” was

rolling on the verge of disintegration. Ottoman Empire became increasingly dependent on the European powers and these powers were allegedly trying to establish direct links with the various segments of the population. Meanwhile they also established connections with the Jews to protect their trade and religious rights. According to Albert Hyamson:

“This question of British protection of Jews became, however, and remained for many years the principal concern of the British Consulate in Jerusalem.”²²

British had their own economic, political, and strategic interests behind all these efforts of protection and connections. At that time British proposed the idea of separate settler state in the Arab land to serve its nefarious and colonial motives. This idea of colonial state in Palestine was propagated by a number of prominent leaders, statesmen, military leaders and philosophers. These colonial motives pave a way for the movement like Zionism.

These Western interests, socio-political developments in nineteenth century and anti-Semitism movement provided the necessary background for the emergence of Zionism. These circumstances encouraged the idea of separate homeland in the minds of Jews and they began to politically unite and organize. In these circumstances, Moses Hess (1812-1875) considered to be the earliest founders of the Zionism gave the idea of “Reconstitution the national center in Palestine” in 1862. In fact, his major writing *Rome and Jerusalem-The last National Question* is considered a most important Zionist Writing which relates the idea of European nationalism with that of Jewish nationalism. Another Zionist, Leo Pinscher, advocated the idea of “auto-emancipation” in 1882 in his pamphlet. Many groups called the, Lovers of the Zion, emerged in Eastern Europe. They used the Zion as a symbol of hope and divine promise because the area where Hazrat Solomon built the temple was referred to the Zion. During 1880 some Jews emigrated to the Palestine with the aim of rebuilding the ancient Jewish “kingdom of Solomon and David”. They thought that Jews shouldn’t migrate to the America or Canada from Europe where they would become strangers again. Instead they should go to the Palestine. After the pogroms and persecution that swept across the Eastern Europe, Jews were more interested in migration to the United States and Canada rather Palestine. The objective of the nation building, by and large, couldn’t make a place among the European Jews. The famous rich Jewish family, The Rothschild, provided the necessary financial assistance to minimize the Jewish immigrants from Western Europe to America. They tried to convert this immigration towards the Palestine. In 1882, three Zionist inspired groups arrived in Palestine and they settled in Jerusalem and Jaffa. Some opened small business other showed interest in farming. The presence of immigrants was noted by the locals because their attempts to purchase land threatened the local population with displacement. Land purchase was a supreme objective of Zionism. Zionists thought without ownership of the land, Eretz Yisrael, never become the Jewish. They adopted any means to get the land by money, by force or via governmental support. The Zionists established the ten settlements in Palestine during the 1880s, four in the North six and in the South. In 1890s, another seven were added in the North and three in the South. By 1908 there were around six thousand Jews in Jaffa and two thousands in Haifa, both previously almost completely Arab cities.²³ During this time a young Viennese journalist came on the stage of history of the Zionism. He converted all these endeavors of different Jews into a single platform of Zionism. He wrote his famous book” Jewish State” which inspired the views of other Jews across the globe. These Jews wanted to establish an Israel State with the support and

under the umbrella of colonial powers and wealthy Jews. At this time, two major strands of the Zionist movement emerged on the screen of history, political and practical. The practical movement favoured the tradition of migration to Palestine. It wanted to establish a Jewish community in Palestine slowly but peacefully through migration. The political Zionism stressed the need for an independent Jewish State and it was less committed to the land of Palestine. It was actually prepared to accept, any vacant space and where it was possible, under the European control. These two strands though opposite in mechanism but the goal was the same, Jewish State. On the one hand, the endless process of settlement of Jewish refugees continued, on the other hand political struggle and connivance with the colonial powers continued. The first Zionist Congress under the presidency of Herzl at Basle in 1897 marked an important turning point in the history of Zionism. Herzl devised a plan which he believed would win the support of European colonial powers. He was well aware of the rivalry between Britons, France and Russia in Middle East. In his keynote address he said "We want to lay the foundation stone of house which is to shelter the Jewish Nation and seeks to obtain for the Jewish people a publicly, recognized and legally secure homeland in Palestine."²⁴ Successful conduction of the Congress gave new impetus to the movement and political Zionism had evidently won an important victory. To conclude the Congress, Herzl wrote in his diary:

"If I were to sum up the Basle Congress in one world-which I shall not do openly- it would be this: At Basle I founded the Jewish State. If I were to say this today I would be met by a universal laughter. In five years, perhaps, and certainly in fifty, everyone will see it."²⁵

This objective could be achieved through organization, colonization and negotiations under the umbrella of Imperial powers. This was well aware that without the patronage of Imperial powers it would be difficult to have nation state as well as protecting it thereafter. Both, Zionists and British Empire, joined hands together for their colonial and cruel objectives. The nexus of Zionistic colonialism and British imperialism opened the doors of Palestine to the Jews for Jewish Settle State, resulted in the disposition and expulsion of native Palestinians. This nexus served both the parties to achieve their motives. From 1881 to 1914 millions of Jews immigrated from Italy, Russian and Eastern Europe to America, Canada, Germany and Africa. More prejudiced and extremists turned to Palestine. The Jews of Europe formed an organization which collected money and funds to organize the immigrants in different parts of the world. Lord Rothschild family played a key role in all these activities. This unity created Jewish stronghold in the America, Britain, Germany, Canada and Argentina. When the Jews came form the Europe, they were in poor condition and in need of money due to their miserable plight. But very soon they became so prosperous that they took over the commercial markets of New York, London and Berlin. Wherever they founded any opportunity to earn they grab it and flourished.

Imperialist-Zionist Nexus:

From 1517 until the 20th century Ottoman Empire was the ruling power in the Middle East. The history of imperial involvement in the Middle East sheds light on the political motivation behind the relationship between Western powers and the Ottoman Empire. Due to its geo-graphical positioning Arab land had gain the most attention by all the imperial powers. Towards the nineteenth century, "Sick man of the Europe" was getting weak with each passing day and European imperialists were looking at the Middle East with enticing eyes. In the mid 1800s, following the Anglo-Turkish agreement the process

of British and other Western powers into the Ottoman economy increased. As the influence of Western powers increased in the economy, the Ottoman industry and economy reached on the verge of collapse. War broke out in 1914 and the leading powers of the world collided each other. It was one of the greatest watersheds of 20th century geo-political history. During the war Imperial Powers, Britain, France and Russia, reached to a secret agreement for the division of Ottoman Empire spoils after its disintegration. This agreement was held in 1916 and known as Sykes-Picot Agreement.

“Under Sykes-Picot, the Syrian coast and much of modern-day Lebanon went to France; Britain would take direct control over central and southern Mesopotamia, around the Baghdad and Basra provinces. [Palestine](#) would have an international administration, as other Christian powers, namely Russia, held an interest in this region. The rest of the territory in question—a huge area including modern-day Syria, Mosul in northern Iraq, and Jordan—would have local Arab chiefs under French supervision in the north and British in the south. Also, Britain and France would retain free passage and trade in the other’s zone of influence.”²⁶

Keeping in mind all these historical developments, now find out the roots of Zionist-Imperialist relations. After the Basle Congress, Herzl kept on finding the imperial power to assist in the Zionist project in Palestine. First he thought to bribe the Sultan Abdul Hameed II of Turkey. Because of the indebtedness of the Ottoman Empire, Herzl suggested to help relieve the financial hardships facing the Sultan in return for his permission to establish a settlement near Jerusalem. The Sultan was agreed to settle them as Ottoman citizens in any place of the Empire but not in Palestine. But Herzl kept insisting and said Palestine was considered the cradle of the Jews alone hence they had the desire to return to it. But the Sultan refused to agree and no amount of assistance seemed to entice the Sultan. He said, “I am unable to compromise one foot of the Holy Land because it is not my possession, it is a possession of my people. Let the Jews keep their millions. If my Empire is torn apart they obtain a part of it. But they first begin the dismemberment of our dead bodies, and I would not allow this while I am alive.”²⁷ After that Herzl approached the German Kaiser Wilhelm II. Wilhelm was not interested in the proposal of Herzl. He told Herzl that he would not make any representation with the Sultan in any matter concerning the Jewish plan in Palestine because that would be considered an intervention into the internal affairs of the Ottoman state.

Britain was most interested in the land of Palestine as it had colonies in the neighbouring countries as well as interests in trade routes and possession of the Suez Canal. Britain joined hands with Zionism to use Jewish community influence for British interests and on the other hand Zionism had a guarantee to have their national state in Palestine which was secured by Britain. Both have the same colonial interests which brought them together to make an alliance. Herzl explained to Britain that, by supporting Zionism they would have favours of all the Jews all around the globe. Jews will also be loyal to the Kingdom and will place themselves at the service of their strategic interests. After Herzl’s death, Dr Weizmann succeeded to get the leadership of the World Zionist Organization. He was well aware that Britain itself wanted a strong foothold in Palestine. Thus in 1904, he moved to England and convinced that Britain was most likely to provide support for the Zionist project. Ottoman’s alliance with Germany in 1914 was not considered a wise decision and it had far-reaching effects on Palestine. It gave Zionism a prime opportunity to negotiate

with British for their national homeland. They emphasized the importance of having inhabitants in Arab by Britain and showed their willingness to secure their strategic interests in the region. After that British policy towards the Zionism changed significantly and they opened official talks with the Zionist leaders. Mr. Weizmann was also a scientist and helped the Britain to invent synthetic acetone for war need and rest was the history.²⁸ Fifteen years later after the Herzl, his successor Weizmann obtained patronage and protection of British imperialist for a Jewish National State, Balfour Declaration in 1917. It was issued to Lord Rothschild in the form of letter for the support of Jewish National State. This 67 words letter was, undoubtedly, one of the most decisive and influential document of twentieth century in the modern history of Palestine and Middle East. It was the cornerstone and a grand victory for the Zionist but for Palestine it was a great tragedy. It changed not only the demographic map but also political and social configuration of the region. The way was now broadened for both British and Zionist to pursue their ambitions. After the second World war, the League of Nations granted mandate to Britain and France over Ottoman territories in 1922.

“The Mandate system was instituted by the League of Nations in the early 20th century to administer non-self-governing territories. The mandatory power, appointed by an international body, was to consider the mandated territory a temporary trust and to see to the well-being and advancement of its population.”²⁹

Imperial Powers, with the help of League of Nations, distributed the Ottoman Empire like a piece of cake and Britain obtained the mandate over Palestine. Under mandate, the Zionist Organization soon became the Jewish Agency and despite being a foreign body, was allowed to assume governmental functions in Palestine. British policy makers had long concluded that Zionist colony in Palestine would serve their interests better than an independent Palestinian state. They started to create suitable circumstances for Zionistic colonialism.³⁰ British mandate facilitated Jewish immigration and encouraged massive settlement by Jews in Palestine. By doing so it did not only lay the foundation of the Jewish state but also sowed the seeds of a conflict that would haunt Palestine and the entire region for many years to come. Such migration led to restlessness among the local Palestinians. Situation became tense and complex in the territory. British government formed a commission of inquiry in 1936 to investigate the ground situation. This Commission was headed by Lord Peel. Commission proposed two state partition plan and suggested that mandate had become unworkable. Arabs totally rejected the plan and the wave of anger ran all over the Palestine among people. The situation became worst due to Arab revolt. At that time Britain felt that losing Arab confidence in the Middle East was not worth it and result in the publication of infamous White Paper in 1939 in which Britain called for a united Palestine rather than a partition.³¹ Freedom should be given that Palestine will free within 10 years and further influx of Jews will be limited. Both the parties didn't accept this paper due to their concerns. Actually Britain played a double game with Arabs and the Jews. They promised with Arabs to support them against Ottoman Empire and as a result they would have sole control over Arab land. On the other hand they promised with Jews to favoure them in war and as a result they will assist them in gaining Jewish state in Palestine. Actually they sold a same horse to two different customers and now in turmoil how to settle it. The situation became more complex after the Adolph Hitler holocaust. Genocide of millions of Jews accelerated the process of migration towards the Palestine. According to the census in 1922, 78% were Muslims and

11% was the Jews in the respective territory. This ratio was changed dramatically in two decade. The percentage of Jews was increased upto 31%. West and Jews proclaimed that the extension of Jews was actually escaping from Nazi persecution, whereas, Arabs viewed Jewish migration as political issue rather than humanitarian. With the passage of time, Jewish insurgency against native Arabs and hostility crossed ever limit. In 1947 Britain handed over the Palestine problem to the United Nations. British Imperialism nurtured and supported the Zionist almost for thirty years. After the 2nd Word War, new imperial power, United States, emerged and the Zionist decided to switch the alliance. As one Western power retreated, another power rushed to the foreground, Zionist made the wisest decision to change its ally. In words of David Ben-Gurion:

“I had no doubt that the center of gravity of our political efforts had shifted from great Britain to America who was making sure of being the world’s leading power, and where the greatest number of the Jews as well as the most influential were to found.”³²

If the League of Nation was an instrument to serve British-Zionist alliance, the United Nations was selected to secure the interests of American-Zionist entente.

Pierced Dagger, Israel:

Fragmentation of the Middle East and the way in which Arabs were divided and their Muslim unity was torn apart is a clear evidence of anti-Islam and the establishment of Israel. In 1st World War, Jews were with the British imperialism but in 2nd War they strategically switched its ally and sat in the cradle of United States. After the war, British Empire was disintegrated and the empire on which sun was not set, now it was impossible for it to rise again. It had knelt before the Jewish conspiracy at the behest of the United States but it didn’t come out openly due to some certain reasons. First Britain couldn’t afford the anger of the Arabs in the Middle East. Second, they didn’t want to lose control over the oil reservoirs.³³ In 1942, American Zionist Organization held a conference in New York chaired by David Ben-Gurion and demanded a separate Jewish National State. The Biltmore Declaration received handsome support from American society, statesmen and businessmen. In this declaration they not only demanded the separate homeland but also rejected the famous 1939 White Paper. They also demanded the unlimited migration of Jews under their control. Now British made some efforts to bring peace in the territory but all in vain. The militant groups of Zionists made serious attacks on British officials and local Arabs to show their muscles because American imperialism backed them. President Truman refused to support all the efforts of peace taken by the Britain and under the influence of Jews began to pave the way for the establishment of Jewish state secretly. He refused the British’s Provincial Autonomy Scheme and allowed more than 25000 Jews to migrate to America. Thus in 1947, Britain officially announced to handed the conflict of Palestine over to the United Nations. Shortly thereafter Arab states wrote to the Secretary General to add special agenda about the independence of Palestine after the mandate ended. But their request was turned down and United Nations Special Committee on Palestine (UNSCOP) was formed by the General Assembly to resolve the issue on 15 May 1947. This committee visited Palestine and its main agenda was to find the ways to resettlement of Jews. As expected, HAC (Higher Arab Council) refused to cooperate with the UNSCOP or several reasons. Foremost among these was their dissatisfaction with the UN for not terminating the mandate and declaring Palestinian independence. In the same manner, they also objected to the notion of linking the Jewish refugee problem with the future of Palestine. On the other hand, Zionists allegedly

influenced the committee by every means. On 31 August 1947, UNSCOP submitted its report and proposed that mandate should be terminated and Palestine should be partitioned into two states, one Arab state and the other Jewish. The religious character of all holy sites be preserved. HAC rejected this proposed plan and declared that these recommendations were contrary to the most fundamental principles of truth and justice as well as the national rights and aspirations of the Palestinian natives. On November 1947, "the UN General Assembly adopted the Resolution 181(11), which recommended the partition of Palestine by vote of 33 in favour, 13 against and 10 abstentions. The Resolution granted 57% of the area of Palestine to the Jews who were only 33% of the population and owned 6% of the land. The Arabs were awarded a state in what was equivalent to 43% of the area of Palestine. The city of Jerusalem was to be placed under international region."³⁴ Arab world collectively rejected the Resolution and thought it was done by UN under the influence of American-Zionist entente. By allowing this resolution the UN violated the foremost charter namely "respect for the principle of equal rights and self determination of people" (Article 1). Jews were overwhelmed with joy and a sense of accomplishment with celebrations in the streets of Jerusalem. Zionist leaders worked tirelessly and continued to execute the plan of achieving their objectives. They carried out some serious attacks not only on Arabs to evacuate but also on British officials. The kid to whom the Britain feed and nurse, now was showing his muscle and eyes under the influence of new imperial power, United States. They began an all out attack with psychological order in order to create an atmosphere of terror and hysteria. Their plan began to succeed. These attacks were evidently the result of political decisions taken by the Zionist leadership rather than responses provoked by military necessity. The first Prime Minister of Israel, David Ben- Gurion, advocated the destruction of the Palestinian society in all its dimensions as a precondition for the creation of a Jewish state on its ruins.³⁵ When Britain ended its rule over Palestine on 15 May there were already three hundred thousand evicted Palestinians in the Jordan Valley, Lebanon, and Syria.

On 14 May 1948, Britain renounced the mandate over Palestine and few minutes later David Ben-Gurion proclaimed the birth of the 'State of Israel. President of United States Harry Truman acknowledged the new state within no time. The joyous moment of the Jews met with the resistance from the Arab population and neighbouring countries. They opposed the establishment of the Israel and viewed it as a violation of their basic rights. The Arab-Israel war ensued, leading to significant territorial changes. Despite facing initial challenges, Israel managed to survive and expands its borders beyond the UN-proposed partition plan. One can easily understand that Israel had the assistance of imperial power at its back otherwise it seemed impossible for a new born country to not only survive but also extended its borders in crucial time. This conflict displaced hundreds of thousands of Palestinians, contributing to the ongoing conflict and shaping the complex geographical dynamics of the Middle East. Arabs know this phenomenon of displacement and dispossession of the Palestinians population as "Nakba". It is an Arabic word means 'catastrophe' and a key factor in the Israel-Palestine conflict. Palestinians view the Nakba as a tragic event that resulted in the loss of their homes, livelihoods and communities. The refugees and their descendants, now numbering in the millions, have been unable to return to their ancestral homes, contributing to the ongoing complexity of the conflict. Acknowledging and addressing the consequences of the Nakba is crucial for any comprehensive efforts toward peace.

Conclusion:

On the basis of discussion in previous pages, an attempt has been made to prove that Zionist movement was based on colonial ideology which successfully established the state of Israel with the help of imperial powers. Due to its geo-graphical positioning and political circumstances, British were looking at Palestine with enticing eyes. They had conspiracy with the Jews and decided to establish Jewish colonial state in Palestine. Massive emigration of Jews was continued under British mandate and accelerated after Nazism. After emerging of America, new imperial power, Zionistic leadership changed their ally. This strategy, change of masters, proved fruitful to them. United Nations was their instrument to fulfill their nefarious objectives and they succeed in 1948. Without the support of Imperial Powers it was impossible for the Jews to have a separate homeland in Palestine. Palestinians became homeless and stateless after the establishment of the state of Israel. It's a complex issue with deep-rooted tensions, including disputes over borders, refugees, and the status of Jerusalem. Peace efforts, including the Camp David Accords in 1978 and the Oslo Accords in the 1990s, aimed at addressing the deep-seated issues, have had limited success in achieving a lasting resolution. The quest for a lasting solution remains a significant challenge.

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